

Dynamic performance of the standalone wind power driven heat pump

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Abstract

Reducing energy consumption and increasing use of renewable energy in the building sector are crucial to the mitigation of climate change. Wind power driven heat pumps have been considered as a sustainable measure to supply heat for detached houses, especially those that even don't have access to the grid. This work is to investigate the dynamic performance of a heat pump system directly driven by a wind turbine. The heat demand of a detached single family house was simulated in details. According to the simulations, the wind turbine is not able to provide the electricity demanded by the heat pump all the time due to the intermittent characteristic of wind power. To solve it, an electric energy storage system was included. Obviously, increasing the size of battery can always reduce the probability of load loss. However, different from the energy storage system, increasing the capacity of wind turbines is not necessary to reduce the probability of load loss instead, due to the different start-up speeds for different capacities of wind turbines. In order to maximize the system benefit, it is of great importance to optimize the capacity of the wind turbine and the size of the energy storage system simultaneously based on dynamic simulations.

Keywords: wind power, heat pump, dynamic performance, space heating, standalone system, probability of load loss

1 Introduction

Today, the building sector has consumed more energy than the industry sector, the transport sector, the agriculture and non-energy use sector, accounting for more than one third of the world's energy consumption [1]; and more than 50% is used for space heating and cooling [2]. In Sweden, the energy consumption for space heating and domestic hot water (DHW) production reached 100TWh in 2014 [3]. Sweden has already set a target to reduce it by 20% by 2020 and 50% by 2050 comparing to the level in 1995 [4]. In order to achieve a sustainable development, reducing energy consumption in the building sector is playing an important role.

In Sweden, there are different ways to supply heat, such as district heating (DH), and using heat pumps (HP), electrical radiator, and biomass/oil/gas boilers. Even though, DH is the most common way to supply heat, accounting for more than 50% of the total heat demand, there are still many single family houses that are not connected the DH network. Heat pumps represent an energy efficiency technology for heat production; however, the share of HP in the Swedish heat market is not very high unfortunately, only covering a little more than 20% of the heat demand [5]. Meanwhile, although there is a tiny share of power from fossil fuel in Sweden, nuclear power accounts for a big proportion, more than 40% [6]. Nevertheless, nuclear power will be phased out in Sweden, therefore, more power should be explored from other renewable resources, such as wind power. Wind power has experienced a fast growth in the past 10 years. The installed capacity in 2014 was 10 times of that in 2004, reaching 5.5 GW. In such a context, developing wind power driven heat pumps (WP-HP) is of significance to achieve the Swedish energy target in 2020 and 2050. In addition, wind potential is usually high during winter, in which the

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heat demand is high; therefore, combining wind power and heat pumps is a win-win technical solution. Moreover, there are also some detached houses that even don't have access to the electricity grid. For such houses, WP-HP is more attractive.

There have been some studies about WP-HP. Jwo et al. have experimentally investigated the performance of a WP-HP system. A method to improve the energy efficiency was proposed [7]. Hedegaard et al. studied the potential of wind power integrating using individual heat pumps and thermal energy storage [8]. According to the brief literature review, there has been little information about the dynamic operation about the WP-HP. No detailed energy demand of detached houses was considered. In addition, due to the intermittent characteristic of WP, even though an energy storage is considered, there is no guarantee of a satisfying indoor thermal comfort. However, there has been no available study about it. To bridge the identified knowledge gaps, this paper is to evaluate the dynamic performance of the standalone wind power driven heat pump. Both the power output of wind and heat demand are modelled in details dynamically. The probability of load loss is used as a key performance indicator. The results will provide insights and guidelines concerning the development of the standalone wind power driven heat pump.

2 Methodology

2.1 System description

As shown in Fig 1, a heat pump system driven by a standalone wind turbine is used to supply heat to a detached house. To handle the intermittent characteristic of wind power, an electric energy storage system was included. In this work, it was assumed that heat is only supplied during October and March.

1.1. House model

A typical Swedish house model was built in IDA ICE [9] to simulate the dynamic heat demand. The house is located in Stockholm and is South-facing. It composes of two floors, including one living room, one kitchen, one laundry, two bathrooms, one office, two kid's rooms, one double bedroom, one hall way and one relax room, and has a total area of 153 m². Some general information about the house is listed in Table 1. The mean door of the house has a size of 2.2m x 1.5m and the back door that is in the opposite side of the main one is 2.1m x 1m. Lights with a power of 50W are chosen for each room, and it is assumed there are 3 lights in the kitchen and the living room, 5 lights in the relax room, 1 light in the laundry and 2 lights in the other rooms. The type of window is triple glazed. The size of windows for different rooms are summarized in Table 1.

Fig. 1 standalone wind power driven heat pump

Table 1. General information about the detached house.

Total floor area 153 m ²
Occupants 4
Total external wall area 142.6 m ²
Total windows area 38.9 m ²
Total heated volume 374.8 m ³
Ceiling height, ground floor 2.5 m
Ceiling height, upper floor 2.4 m
Average U-value 0.5028 W/m ² K
Window SHGC 0.68, U-value 1.9 W/m ² K
Air tightness 0.5 ACH

Table 2. Windows dimensions and location.

Bedroom1	1.45m x 1.247m and 1.45m x 0.623m
Bedroom2	two of 1.45m x 1.247m
Double room	two of 1.45m x 1.247m
Bathroom2	1.45m x 1.247m and 1.45m x 0.623m
Relax zone	2.6m x 1.2m and 2m x 1.247m
Kitchen	1.45m x 1.247 and 2.9m x 1.247m
Living room	2.9m x 1.247m and 2m x 1.247m
Office	2.9m x 1.247m
Laundry	two of 1.45m x 1.247m
Bathroom	0.25m x 0.96m
Hall way	0.25m x 0.96m

2.2 Heat pump model

An in-house model was developed to simulate the thermodynamic performance of a heat pump at different ambient temperatures in Matlab. R410a, as a common working fluid for heat pumps, was selected. The model was validated by comparing the simulated results with experimental data and the coefficient of performance (COP) provided by heat pump companies. Based on this model, the COP was correlated to the ambient temperature as the following equation:

$$COP = 2.79 + 0.036 * T_{am} + 6.036 * 0.0001 * T_{am}^2$$

where T_{am} (°C) is the ambient temperature.

When the heat demand is obtained from the house model, the corresponding power demand can be estimated by using the COP calculated from the above equation.

2.3 Wind turbine model and Energy storage

The dynamic simulations of the wind turbine system have been conducted with the following assumptions: if the wind speed is lower than the wind turbine cut-in speed, the power production is null; similarly, if the wind speed exceeds the cut-out speed, the power production is null; if the wind speed is equal or greater than the rated speed, the power produced is equal to the rated power; if the wind speed is lower than the rated wind speed and at the same time greater than the cut-in speed, the wind turbine power output is given by the following relationship:

$$P = a \cdot v^3 - b \cdot P_r$$

where, P_r is the rated power and a and b are two coefficients calculated according to following equations:

$$a = \frac{P_r}{v_r^3 - v_c^3} \quad b = \frac{v_c^3}{v_r^3 - v_c^3}$$

where, v_c is the cut-in speed, and v_r is the rated wind speed. The battery overcomes the mismatching between power production and consumption. The battery model is based on an energy balance defined by the following equations for the charging and discharging process, respectively:

$$\text{Charging} : C_{bat}(t) = C_{bat}(t-1) \cdot (1 - \sigma) + \left(E_{WG}(t) - \frac{E_L(t)}{\eta_{inv}} \right) \eta_{bat}$$

$$\text{Discharging} : C_{bat}(t) = C_{bat}(t-1) \cdot (1 - \sigma) - \left(\frac{E_L(t)}{\eta_{inv}} - E_{WG}(t) \right)$$

where $C_{bat}(t)$ is the capacity of the battery at the time step t , $C_{bat}(t-1)$ is the capacity of the battery at the time step $(t-1)$, $E_{WG}(t)$ is the power produced by the wind turbine, $E_L(t)$ is the electric load, η_{inv} the efficiency of the inverter and η_{bat} the efficiency of the battery. It was assumed that the maximum depth of discharge is 20%, the efficiency of the inverter is 90%, the efficiency of the battery is 75% and the self-discharge rate σ is 0,02%.

3 Results

The simulated energy demand of the house based on the hourly climatic data is illustrated in Fig 2. This energy demand is mainly used for space heating, DHW and lighting; while the energy consumption of cooking and other electronic appliances, such as washing machines, TV and fridges, was not considered. The need of space heating and DHW increases along the drop of the ambient temperature. Since January has the lowest monthly average ambient temperature, it has the highest energy demand. Fig 3 shows the electricity demand and the power generation from the wind turbine with a capacity of 7kW.

Fig 2 total energy demand of the detached house during the heating season

Fig 3 Electricity demand vs power output of the wind turbine during the heating season

Due to the intermittent characteristic of wind power, the wind turbine cannot always satisfy the demand of heat pump. However, it is also clear that there can be a large surplus power output when the wind is strong. This extra part can be stored and used for the time when there is insufficient power output from the wind turbine. The electrical energy storage system is designed according to the number of Days of Autonomy (DA), which means how many days the heat pump can run on the support of battery. To evaluate the system performance, the probability of load loss (POLL), defined as the ratio of the number of hours when the energy system (wind turbine and battery) cannot meet the demand (energy system failure) to the total number of operation hours, is used. When the load loss happens, the indoor temperature can drop below the desired temperature, which is set as 18°C in this study. It implies that the indoor thermal comfort will be violated. POLL was assessed for different sizes of battery and capacities of wind turbine and the results are displayed in Fig 4. Naturally, POLL is lower when the size of the electrical energy storage system is larger, as a larger energy storage can store more power; and the relation between POLL and DA is almost linear. However, it is interesting to note that raising the capacity of the wind turbine may not result in a smaller POLL. This is due to the different requirements about the start-up speed for different capacity wind turbines (wind-power curve matching). It is clear from Fig 4, when the capacity of the wind turbine is increased from 6kW to 10kW, at the same DA number, POLL first drops and then rises. A larger capacity wind turbine surely needs a higher investment cost, therefore, it is important to do dynamic simulations before the size of the system can be determined. In addition, when increasing the wind turbine capacity from 6kW to 8kW, POLL can be slightly decreased; whereas, the same reduction of POLL may be achieved by increasing the size of energy storage with a much lower cost. However, if the wind turbine capacity is too small, there may not be enough extra power generation for charging a large energy storage system, resulting waste of storage capacity.

Fig 4 probability of load loss per battery size for different size of turbines

4 Conclusions

This paper studied the dynamic performance of a heat pump system directly driven by wind power, based on the simulated heat demand of a detached single family house. Due to the intermittent characteristic of wind power, the wind turbine cannot always satisfy the electricity demand of the heat pump; however, a large surplus power output also exists when the wind is strong and the extra electricity generation can be stored in energy storage systems. It is obvious that increasing the size of energy storage systems can reduce the probability of load loss; nevertheless, increasing the capacity of wind turbines may not have the same effect, due to the different start-up speeds of difference capacity wind turbines. In order to maximize the system benefit, the capacity of the wind turbine and the size of the energy storage system should be optimized simultaneously based on dynamic simulations.

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